

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF TEACHING PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS BASED ON INTERACTIVE EDUCATIONAL METHODS

Abstract. In this article, teaching primary school students through the use of teaching methods, teaching ways of forming students' worldview, cooperation between teachers and students in the educational process, education - issues of education and the organization of educational activities in an interesting way so that today's youth can think independently were thought about.

Key words: education, interactive methods, student, teacher, cooperation, teaching, lesson, pedagogical skill.

Introduction.

In the world, it is considered an important task to offer the most optimal ways to modernize the modern primary school education. In this regard, the memorandum of the international symposium of UNESCO "Fundamental (scientific and humanistic) university education"; Conclusions of regional conferences held by UNESCO in 1996-1998; Conclusions of the first World Conference on Education in Havana, Dakar, Tokyo, Palermo, Beirut (Paris, October 1998); State educational standards of primary education, most importantly, the process of systematization of primary school students' assessment of their abilities in reading (EGRA) and mathematics (EGMA) primary education led to the actual introduction of the new structure in lim. The content of these documents defines the strategic and main goal of primary education. It is necessary to use modern and high-quality approaches to the educational process based on preserving the fundamental nature of education for students, following educational approaches and effective world experience, demonstrating their capabilities, and meeting their needs.

In our country, it is emphasized that comprehensive development of elementary school students, activation of their cognitive activity in the educational process serves as one of the main factors in the development of society. From this point of view, in the strategy of New Uzbekistan, "... increasing the prestige of education in society and encouraging young people's pursuit of perfection - this is education to achieve stable and consistent development, to turn schools into centers of true spirituality and enlightenment, culture - application of interactive methods of education" is defined as an important task. In order to fulfill this task, it is important to approach education

based on the humanitarian principle, taking into account the opportunities, interests, and abilities of primary school students. Also, it is an urgent task to expand the possibilities of forming the abilities and intellectual potential of the student within his own capacity.

Literature review (Literature review). We know that primary school is the most important part of the educational process. The main task of a modern school is to bring out the abilities of each student on the basis of high technologies, to form a conscious attitude to life and work, to educate a person worthy of society, to deliver competitive personnel to the world arena. School education should prepare every child to set serious goals for himself, to show his abilities, to independently respond skillfully to various life situations.

Analyzing the pedagogical views of Eastern and Western scholars, we see that they emphasize that the teacher plays an important role in the growth of students, the effective development of their logical and independent thinking skills. In addition, they showed that it is necessary to use pedagogical tools and present assignments taking into account the child's characteristics in the process of teaching.

A number of points are analyzed in modern studies regarding this problem. The problem of activating students' cognitive activity, using the student's opportunities for education R. Jorayev, E. Sattorov, R. Safarova, T. Gafforova, Sh. Nurullayeva, V. Karimova, E. Ghaziyev, D.D. Blagoi, P.P. Blonsky, N.M. Verzilina, P.A. Henkel, N.K. Goncharova, A.V. Lunacharsky, M.A. Prokofiev, D.A. Einstein, N.M. Shakhmayeva, I.E. The results of scientific research of Unt and other scientists allow to determine the conceptual apparatus.

T.T. Ganiyev analyzed the ways to improve students' cognitive activity by performing various creative tasks and individual exercises offered according to the student's level of knowledge [2].

I.M. Yastrebov, first of all, emphasizes the role of education in child development, in his opinion, revealing and improving abilities is part of education [3].

In our opinion, the application of interactive methods to the modern educational process in the development of students' thinking and the activation of their level of knowledge is of particular importance in connection with the profiling of all stages of primary school.

Research methodology and analysis (Research Methodology). Even with any teaching method and effectively organized lesson, some students progress quickly and successfully, while others move forward slowly and with great difficulty. Some achieve high results and great success without spending a lot of effort and time, while others cannot rise to the same level with all their desires. All this shows the different abilities of students in relation to educational activities.

The difference between classes based on innovative pedagogical technology and traditional classes is that they create an atmosphere of freedom

for the student and give him the opportunity to freely express his opinion. How is this opportunity created? A friendly learning environment is created by asking questions without putting any pressure on the student and without affecting his personality. The most important "core" part of the educational process based on pedagogical technology - starting each lesson with the development of rules based on the purpose of the lesson helps the educational process to be productive and orderly. At this stage of the lesson, it is necessary to invite students to come up with ideas and suggestions and at the same time write down all ideas and suggestions. The rules, which are written as briefly and clearly as possible, are explained by the students (with the help of the teacher). On the board, you can write the following rules for this step:

- *DO NOT CRITICIZE OR EVALUATE* (no participant may discuss, evaluate or criticize the opinions of others);
- *NO WRONG ANSWERS* (don't be afraid to make mistakes);
- *CHANGE, IMPROVE, JUSTIFY* (make changes to the opinion of others, add. Justify your opinion);
- *KEEP CALM, PARTICIPATE AND ENJOY* (An environment of mutual support and friendly competition is created).

In the educational process, if necessary, it is necessary to remind the students about the rules and ideas, as a facilitator, to guide and encourage them.

Innovative technology is a process that develops rational ways of the educational system, in which the teacher is considered the main responsible person. Because its main task is to deliver information to students in a fast, clear and understandable way. The teacher should teach students to think independently, observe, and draw conclusions regardless of their ability to receive news and their inclinations and character. The changes and innovations taking place in the education system, in addition to providing new knowledge, skills and qualifications to students, also envisage the change of our youth towards themselves and other people, society, state, nature, and inculcate patriotic ideas in their minds and hearts. This process is carried out by instilling the rich spiritual heritage, traditions and traditions of our people into the heart of the student.

Analysis and results (Analysis and results). In order to determine the level of independent thinking, the breadth of worldviews, the speed of thinking and the talent of elementary school students based on interactive methods, we also used the following "Game-Puzzle".

For this, the teacher asks the students 3 riddles or definitions with the same answer. Students write "Question 1" on their answer sheets. On the bottom, they write "Answer 1", "Answer 2", "Answer 3" and after each riddle (definition) is read, they record the answers on the answer sheets. The first riddle (definition) is tricky, the second riddle (definition) is easier, and the third riddle (definition) is very easy. Intelligent students who can think independently will be able to find the correct answer from the first riddle, and as a result, they

will admit that all three answers are the same. This standard makes it possible to obtain more realistic results and also facilitates scoring. That is, if the correct answer is found from the first riddle (definition), 3 points, if the correct answer is found from the second riddle (definition), 2 points, and finally, if the correct answer is found only on the third attempt, 1 point is awarded. 0 points if no correct answer is found at all.

As a result of these tests, questionnaires, assignments, we tried to evaluate the students' cognitive activity at the following level (Table 1).

Table 1

Current status of students

#	Groups	Number of students	Primary stage (in numbers and percentages)		
			Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
1.	Experimental group	35	6	11	18
2	in %	100 %	17.2 %	31.4 %	51.4%
3.	Control group	40	5	16	19
4	in %	100 %	12.5 %	40 %	47.5 %

As can be seen from the table, the teaching of students with interactive educational methods is not at the required level. Therefore, in the process of teaching primary education subjects, it was found appropriate to use interactive educational methods to motivate students, independence, activity, in relation to the lesson.

Teamwork, individual, group, pair work in the teaching of elementary school students with interactive educational methods, modern pedagogical technologies in the course of the lesson: "Staircase", "Black box", "Cubic", "Colored caps", "Diamond" and game technologies: from game technologies such as "Quiet inquiry", "Educational comics", "Young pedagogue", "Teacher to myself", "Last stage" was used.

We developed a method of conducting lessons in experimental groups (35 people) and focused on compliance with the following conditions:

a) using the content possibilities of the educational material in order to develop the learning activity of students based on interactive educational methods (in order to acquire the content of this or that educational material, it is necessary to select issues that require a certain formation process of the learning activity);

b) ensuring that students' learning activities match their capabilities when completing tasks (such compatibility can be achieved if the educational process is individualized with the help of differentiated examples and problems);

d) maintaining a high level of formation of students' knowledge acquisition activities in the entire educational process (for this purpose, the type of activity of subjects in the lesson should be renewed).

Conclusion

The analysis of existing literature and our observations proved the correctness of the goal we set. That's why we had the opportunity to justify that teaching based on interactive educational methods is one of today's pedagogical problems waiting for its solution to activate the cognitive activity of elementary school students. Our research has clearly shown the need for consistent arming of elementary school students with theoretical knowledge and practical experiences that serve to activate cognitive activity. It was also found that it is important to take into account their age characteristics, mental world, emotions, and capabilities when presenting educational tasks based on interactive educational methods.

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